

Deliverable D1.6

CityCLIM Framework (M36)

WP 1

The CityCLIM framework provides tailored manuals with information and guidelines for all types of CityCLIM users, as for example:

- **city administrations or city planners** who are interested in integrating and using the CityCLIM solution in their city,
- **citizens** who are interested in contributing to CityCLIM as citizen scientists,
- **third party developers** who are interested in developing further components for the Generic City Climate Platform as well as City Climate Services or integrating further data sources.

D1.6 Summary

D1.6 is the second edition of manuals aimed at **developers, third-party software providers, city administrations and city planners**.

Manual 3 - City Administration Services: A User Guide

Description	A comprehensive overview of CityCLIM's City Administration Services, detailing their functions, benefits, and application in urban management.
Target Groups	City administrators and urban planners who want to use of the CityCLIM City Administration Services.

Manual 4 - Development & Integration: A Developer Guide

Description	A comprehensive guide for developers and third party software providers explaining how to integrate their own City Climate Services and components into the CityCLIM ecosystem.
Target Groups	Developers and third-party software providers.

Project website address: <https://www.cityclim.eu/>

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the CityCLIM Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.

© 2024 Copyright in this document remains vested in the CityCLIM Project Partners.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036814

City Administration Services: A User Guide

A comprehensive overview of CityCLIM's City Administration Services, detailing their functions, benefits, and application in urban management.

September 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036814

Foreword

Dear Reader,

Welcome to the user manual of the City Administration Services, a key result of the CityCLIM project. Our initiative is dedicated to providing urban planners and city administrators with advanced tools and insights for effective environmental management in urban settings.

Cities today face a variety of environmental challenges, from heat islands to air pollution. The CityCLIM project addresses these issues head-on, offering a range of services specifically designed to identify, analyse, and mitigate urban environmental concerns. Our suite of services, including Heat Island Identification, City Air Flow Analysis, Pollution Area Detection, and their respective simulation and mitigation strategies, are tailored to empower city administrations or anyone who's involved in making decisions about a city's future with the necessary data and strategies for informed decision-making.

In this user guide, we will delve into each City Administration Service, demonstrating their practical application and effectiveness in real-world scenarios. You will gain insight into how each service operates, the kind of data it provides, and how this information can be leveraged to create healthier, more sustainable urban environments.

Our goal with these services is not just to offer solutions, but to equip decision makers with the means to proactively manage and improve their urban environments through informed planning and strategic implementation, to make cities more liveable and resilient.

Join us as we explore the capabilities and benefits of the City Administration Services under the CityCLIM project, your partner in urban environmental management.

Sincerely,

The CityCLIM Consortium

Table of Contents

- 1 Introduction 5**
- 2 City Administration Services 6**
 - 2.1 Onboarding Procedure 6
 - 2.2 Identification Services..... 8
 - 2.2.1 EO-based Heat Island Identification Service..... 8
 - 2.2.2 UltraHD-based Identification Services 11
 - 2.3 Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Services 15
 - 2.3.1 EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service 15
 - 2.3.2 UltraHD-based Simulation and Mitigation Services..... 18
 - 2.3.3 Simulation Editor 21
- 3 Conclusion and Contact 24**
- 4 References 25**

Abbreviations

2D	two-dimensional	GUI	Graphical User Interface
3D	three-dimensional	i.e.	id est = that is to say
ANN	Artificial Neural Network	LST	Land Surface Temperature
CSV	Comma-separated values	SUHI	Surface Urban Heat Island
D	Deliverable	UFTVI	Urban Thermal Field Variance Index
DI	Discomfort Index	UHII	Urban Heat Island Intensity Index
e.g.	Exempli gratia = for example	UltraHD	Ultra High Definition
EO	Earth Observation	UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
etc.	et cetera.		

1 Introduction

CityCLIM provides cities with specialised data-driven services to understand and address urban climate challenges, such as the Urban Heat Island Effect. This user guide is dedicated to the commercially offered City Administration Services from the service portfolio of the CityCLIM project which support the identification of different aspects of city's climate profile and moreover allow to investigate and evaluate effects of simulated changes to urban areas. The user guide details the functions, benefits, and applications of these services and explains how they enable various key stakeholders, such as government agencies (e.g., environmental, health, planning), building authorities, insurers, or real estate developers, to analyse and simulate urban climate patterns in selected cities.

The City Administration Services are divided into two main categories:

(1.) **Identification Services**, which offer statistical analyses with customisable configurations related to the themes heat, pollution and city airflow, that rely on aggregated results from past UltraHD weather model runs.

(2.) **Simulation and Mitigation Services**, which offer simulation features to estimate and visualise the impact of simulated changes in the urban landscape.

The user guide is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** provides detailed information for using the City Administration Services. It begins with an onboarding procedure in section 2.1, outlining the steps to access the service GUIs. Section 2.2 covers the use of the Identification Services, including the Earth Observation (EO)-based Heat Island Identification Service (2.2.1) and UltraHD-based Identification Services (2.2.2). Section 2.3 explains the use of the Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Services, covering the EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service (2.3.1), the UltraHD-based Simulation and Mitigation Services (2.3.2), and the Simulation Editor (2.3.3).
- **Chapter 3** provides information on where to find further support and how to make contact.

2 City Administration Services

This chapter describes the usage of the City Administration Services. An overview is given in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: Overview of City Administration Services.

City Administration Services	Description	Usage in Section
Identification Services		
EO-based Heat Island Identification Services	Provides Land Surface Temperature (LST) maps and indices using only purely EO data to identify urban heat islands.	2.2.1
UltraHD-based Identification Services	Offers statistical analysis of heat, pollution, and airflow using aggregated UltraHD weather model data.	2.2.2
Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Services		
EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service	Simulates and visualises the impact of urban landscape changes on heat patterns using purely EO data and machine learning.	2.3.1
UltraHD-based Simulation Services	Analyses the effects of mitigation activities on heat, pollution, and airflow through user-manipulated scenarios in UltraHD simulations.	2.3.2
Simulation Editor	A service for manipulating urban characteristics to create scenarios for analysis with UltraHD simulations.	2.3.3

To access these services via the web-based graphical user interfaces (GUIs), an onboarding procedure needs to be completed in advance to get CityCLIM account, described in Section 2.1.

All services are powered by an advanced full-physics weather forecast model processor designed specifically for high-precision, short-term weather forecasting. This focus allows the simulation services to provide accurate, actionable insights for assessing mitigation measures in relation to current local climate conditions that are already influenced by climate change.

The City Administration Services form a substantial part of the implemented workflows within the CityCLIM project, where more detailed information on CityCLIM as a whole can be found in the handbook “Towards a Green Future with CityCLIM: A Handbook for Interested Cities” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2023b) or as short fact sheet in the “Deliverable 6.6 - Optimised City Administration Services” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2024).

2.1 Onboarding Procedure

The access to the CityCLIM City Administration Services requires a prior registration to get a CityCLIM account, which will be used for login as described below. To get the needed links to access the chosen City Administration Services and account management, please get in contact with the CityCLIM administration team in advance (see section 3).

Account Registration

To create a CityCLIM account, access the central account management (see Figure 2-1) using the provided links from the CityCLIM administration team.

Figure 2-1: CityCLIM Account Management Software.

On the homepage click on "Sign In" (see button in the upper right corner in Figure 2-1) to navigate to the sign-in page (see Figure 2-3). On the bottom of the sign-in page click on "Register" to get to the registration page shown in Figure 2-2. Complete the registration form and click on "Register". After a few moments, an email with a confirmation link will be sent. Clicking on this link completes the registration process.

Figure 2-3: Sign-In page.

Login/Sign In

To access the City Administration Services, use the direct links provided by the CityCLIM administration team. If not already logged in, the system will redirect to the sign-in page (see Figure 2-3) for authentication. After logging in, it will redirect back to the originally requested service.

Update Account Information

To change account information, such as name or email address, or to delete the account, navigate to the sign-in page (Figure 2-3), sign in, and on the account page, click "Personal info". In the upcoming page (see Figure 2-4), perform the needed actions.

Figure 2-2: Registration page.

Figure 2-4: Account information.

2.2 Identification Services

The Identification Services offer on-demand statistical analysis of the urban area for heat-related environmental parameters and time specifications, which facilitates the identification of critical local urban areas accordingly. Two service variants based on the beyond-state-of-the-art physical weather model (UltraHD-based; see Section 2.2.2) and purely based on EO data (EO-based; see Section 2.2.1) are available.

2.2.1 EO-based Heat Island Identification Service

The EO-based Heat Island Identification Service provides a remote sensing platform designed to support urban planners and city administrators in managing and monitoring urban heat islands purely based on EO data. Urban heat islands are phenomena that occur in cities due to the accumulation of impervious surfaces and the reduction of green areas, leading to a significant increase in temperature compared to surrounding rural areas.

The service allows users to make informed decisions to mitigate the negative effects of heat in urban areas. By leveraging satellite data and advanced tools, this service helps to identify critical areas with greater heat exposure, track their changes over time, and plan effective adaptation strategies using several indices derived from LST maps.

Each index offers a unique perspective on the impact of heat in urban areas, helping planners assess thermal comfort, temperature distribution, and the intensity of the urban heat island phenomenon. Below are the key indices used in the EO-based Heat Island Identification Service, which are critical for monitoring and informed decision-making.

Available Indices:

- **Discomfort Index (DI):** This index quantifies the combined impact of temperature and humidity on human comfort. It is calculated using temperature and relative humidity. Higher values indicate greater discomfort.
- **Surface Temperature (LST):** Surface temperature, measured from satellite data, provides information on the thermal state of various surfaces, such as urban areas, vegetation, and water bodies. It is essential for monitoring environmental changes and assessing thermal patterns.
- **Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI):** This index measures the difference in surface temperature between urban areas and surrounding rural areas. It highlights how urbanisation affects local temperatures, often revealing higher temperatures in cities due to human activities and modified land surfaces.
- **Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UFTVI):** The UFTVI assesses the variability of surface temperatures within a city. It captures the thermal heterogeneity caused by different land uses, materials, and activities, providing a detailed view of the spatial distribution of heat within urban areas.
- **Urban Heat Island Intensity Index (UHII):** The UHII quantifies the intensity of the urban heat island effect by calculating the temperature difference between urban areas and their rural counterparts. This index is critical for understanding the magnitude of temperature elevation caused by urbanisation.
- **Urban Hot Spots:** Urban hot spots are specific areas within a city that exhibit significantly higher temperatures compared to their surroundings. These zones are identified through LST data and are often associated with high levels of impervious surfaces, lack of vegetation, and concentrated human activities. Identifying urban hot spots is crucial for targeted mitigation strategies.

The following sub-sections describe how to use the features offered by the EO-based Heat Island Identification Service.

2.2.1.1 Visualisation of LST and Urban Heat Indices

The service allows to visualise interactive maps showing LST and derived indices for urban areas.

One of the main functionalities is the visualisation of detailed LST maps which provides access to high-resolution data that displays temperature variations across different parts of the city, allowing users to explore thermal patterns and urban heat concentrations.

Figure 2-5: Parameter selection for map visualisation.

Steps to use the function (compare with Figure 2-5):

- (1) **User and Bounding Box selection:** Select the user id and the corresponding area of interest (bounding box) from the dropdown list.
- (2) **Model parameter selection:** Select the desired index from the dropdown.
- (3) **Timestamp selection:** Select the desired date from the available timestamps on the dropdown list.
- (4) **Map navigation:** Panning and zoom is available to explore different areas in the selected bounding box. Note that dark blue areas indicate missing pixels due to cloud cover or radiometric artifacts on the source satellite data.

The interactive interface enables users to quickly access relevant information, making it easier to identify hotspots and assess the impact of urbanisation on local temperatures. This visual tool is essential for highlighting areas where immediate interventions may be required to reduce heat-related risks.

2.2.1.2 LST and Urban Heat Indices time series exploration

Another key feature of the EO-based Heat Island Identification Service is the comparison of LST data and derived indices through time series analysis. This functionality allows users to select specific points on the map and generate temporal data to monitor temperature trends over time (see Figure 2-6).

Figure 2-6: Time series graphs from EO-Based Heat Island Identification Service.

Steps to use the function (compare with Figure 2-6):

- (1) **Point selection:** Use the icon to enable point selection. Then click on the map to place a marker.
- (2) **Point modification:** Modify or Erase the markers if necessary.
- (3) **Opening Chart Panel:** Click on Chart Icon to show the Chart panel.
- (4) **Parameter Selection:** Select the required parameter and the time of the day (Morning, Afternoon or All Day).
- (5) **Date interval selection:** Select start and end dates.
- (6) **Request a Chart:** Click on Get Time Series button and the chart will be displayed (this may take time depending on the Start and End date interval amplitude).

By comparing data from different periods, planners can better understand seasonal variations, track the effectiveness of mitigation measures, and identify long-term trends in urban heat islands. This tool is invaluable for analysing the evolution of thermal conditions and planning for future environmental challenges.

2.2.2 UltraHD-based Identification Services

The UltraHD-based Identification Services offer statistical analysis using different configuration capabilities related to heat, pollution and city airflow. These analyses rely on aggregated results from past UltraHD weather model runs. Hence, the UltraHD-based Identification Services unify the following services:

- Heat Island Identification Service
- City Air Flow Identification Service
- Pollution Area Identification Service

The main features of the UltraHD-based Identification Services are the following:

- On-demand requests to analyse local urban climate for time periods (e.g., for the last 7 days) that returns an image overlay as a result for the entire urban area
- Line charts comparing specific local urban areas to their exposure to heat, pollution and airflow
- Export functionality for time series data
- Access to already calculated results that prevents re-calculation and allows to share results
- An integrated user guides explaining the functionality and workflows
- Multi-language support

Figure 2-7: View of the UltraHD-based Identification Services showing analysis results for the entire region and specified local areas via a map and line-charts.

The following manual explains how to use the UltraHD-based Identification Services that lead to results presented in Figure 2-7, where the supported parameters are as follows:

- Temperature at 2-metre height
- Dewpoint at 2-metre height
- Surface temperature
- Nitric acid
- Particulate Matter 10
- Nitrogen dioxide
- Ozone
- Airflow

Supporting these parameters, the features of the UltraHD-based Identification Services allow the following:

- Compute heat profiles of urban areas which could be used as indicators for mitigation measures.
- Identify critical areas prone to extreme heat events via a 2D-map.
- Get insights to spatial temperature pattern in urban areas which can be utilised in decision-making processes and for public information regarding heat, pollution, and airflow.
- Analyse climate land-sea interaction when applied to coastal regions.
- Give recommendations of areas with cold winds.
- Understand which urban areas are exposed to harmful pollution.

Figure 2-8: Init view of the UltraHD-based Identification Service.

When entering the UltraHD-based Identification Services (see Figure 2-8), the following options appear:

- (1) Selection of the user and area.
- (2) Configuration of the image analysis (see also Figure 2-9):
 - a) Start and End date of the request time range.
 - b) For each day within the requested time range, daily sections (e.g., every night, every morning section 6-10 AM) can be determined.
 - c) Sampling rate used for the image analysis (e.g. 60 minutes would mean to consider hourly results of the UltraHD model loop).
 - d) Parameter for the image analysis.
 - e) Statistical option for the image analysis, which is applied to the series of values of each grid cell within the requested time range (available are max, min, and mean).

Figure 2-9: Configuration for the on-demand image analysis.

Figure 2-10: View on the UltraHD-based Identification Service showing access to all different service features.

Closing the configuration panel (or executing an image analysis), the following options appear (see also Figure 2-10):

- (1) User, area selection and image analysis configurations.
- (2) Start user guide, which explain the usage and navigation of the service.
- (3) Access to database of already calculated image analysis with filtering option. It is available when if the user and area is selected.
- (4) Time series requests and line charts for specified area (see below). It is available whenever at least one area is specified for the time series request.

Whenever a user and an area are selected, the button (3) is enabled and shows completed image analysis results.

Figure 2-11: Results.

The completed results are presented in a table which supports filtering (e.g. by parameter) (see table in Figure 2-11). Clicking on a row shows the underlying result on the map.

Figure 2-12: Polygons drawn on the map to prepare the comparison of three different local urban areas with respect to their exposure e.g. to temperature at 2m height.

If an image analysis result is present (see Figure 2-12) (i.e., by on-demand request or selected from the database), then the areas can be determined by drawing polygons on the map using (1). Option (2) can be used to move or delete polygons. If at least one polygon is drawn on the map, the time series panel is enabled (see Figure 2-13).

Figure 2-13: Comparison of three local urban areas regarding temperature development at 2m height.

On the time series chart (see Figure 2-13) the following options are available:

- (1) Selection for the demanded time series parameter.
- (2) Sampling rate of the time series with a range of 5 to 120 minutes (e.g., sampling rate of 60 minutes means getting a time series with hourly values).
- (3) Export of the time series data in CSV format.
- (4) Trigger the time series request, which is possible having a time series parameter selected.

After requesting the time series, the result is presented as line charts, where moving the cursor on the graphs shows the values for each location. Moreover, zooming to sections of the line charts is supported.

2.3 Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Services

The “Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Services” allow users to analyse the impact of user-provided simulated changes to urban structure (e.g., planting trees, new buildings) to local climate conditions.

The UltraHD-based services (see section 2.3.2) address urban heat, pollution, and airflow issues, with an additional purely EO-based service variant (see section 2.3.1) on urban heat available.

2.3.1 EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service

The “EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service” offers a simulation tool to estimate and visualise the impact of changes in the urban landscape on urban heat patterns as indicated by the land surface temperature.

This tool was developed to provide a fast and initial overview of the direct effects of future construction projects before they are realised. Multiple options can easily be evaluated as it is needed by city administrations or the interested public.

Since the tool is based on EO data only, its advantages are a short runtime (seconds) and a low effort of implementation for any city worldwide. In comparison to this EO data-based tool, the CityCLIM ecosystem offers another simulation applying UltraHD weather model simulations (UltraHD Heat Island Simulation Service; see section 2.3.2) for the same purpose.

While the EO-based tool was developed to provide first assessments for an unlimited number of user-built scenarios, the UltraHD-version of the tool can be used for a deeper view into selected scenarios as it is expected to provide a higher degree of reliability because of a process-based representation. However, it is computationally very intensive (several hours) and requires a high effort to implement for a specific city.

Technically, the EO-based simulation tool underlies a machine learning model linking LST measurements from the Landsat 8 and 9 satellites to a number of layers characterising the urban land surface that are derived from multispectral Sentinel-2 satellite data (vegetation and built-up indices, distances to vegetation and water), and - if a digital elevation model of a city is existing - the 3D structure of a city. A machine learning model is trained to represent the relationship between LST and the urban characteristics, which is then applied to predict changes in LST upon user-defined changes in the urban configuration. With this, for instance, the effects of sealing a park area on the urban temperature can be assessed and suitable construction alternatives can be explored before the construction is implemented.

Features:

- Evaluation of urban heat upon changes in urban configuration (such as construction scenarios) under typical and extreme summer day conditions of last years
- User-defined changes
- Possible land uses: built-up (when 3D information is included, also building heights), vegetation, and water
- Prediction of changes in LST for the user-defined configuration

The following provides a step-by-step guidance on how to use the tool.

After accessing the tool, **the pilot city is selected** which should be explored (mandatory before any other setting). Below this, 3 tabs are located (named “Info”, “Editor”, “Result”) which correlate to the following 3 steps.

Step 1 “Info”: Select land surface temperature dataset to evaluate

In this first step, users can view and evaluate the land surface temperature patterns in the city. The land surface temperature is the skin temperature of the urban surface as measured by the Landsat 8 and 9 satellites (measured on 100m resolution, although the data product is provided on 30m resolution).

Data are available each for both average and extreme summer day of 2021-2024 so that average summer conditions as well as the condition under past heat waves can be considered.

Perform following steps (compare with Figure 2-14):

- (1) **Select model:** selection of the type of machine learning prediction model which is used within the tool. “ANN_2D” is an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) only including the 2D land surface information (surface type and distance metrics). “ANN_3D” is a model including 3D variables reflecting the building geometry of the city in case a height model was available from the city. Since the addition of the 3D building geometry variables does not provide a significant gain in model prediction accuracy, it is recommended to use “ANN_2D”.
- (2) **Select reference days:** selection of the reference LST dataset to be used in the evaluation, either an average (e.g., “2024_median”) or an extreme summer day (e.g., “2024_max”) of the last years.

The display will show the LST for the selected configuration in °C for the city centre. A layer showing the cities’ buildings provided by Open Street Map is overlaid for orientation.

Figure 2-14: Visualisation of the LST in the EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service (step 1).

Step 2 “Editor”: Draw custom user scenario

In this step, a user can define a new urban configuration as a scenario to evaluate. For instance, a building in a park area can be drawn or a new park or water body can be created instead of housing areas. Here, the spatial resolution of the underlying LST data of 100m should be considered when creating a scenario (although data are given in pixel size of 30m). Therefore, changes in structures should not be too small but at least extent to building blocks rather than isolated houses to see a difference. Multiple polygons can be drawn (e.g. different house blocks) but all polygons of one scenario should be located within the same urban quarter.

Perform following steps (compare with Figure 2-15):

- (1) Press “New”, enter a scenario name and press “Create”
- (2) The polygon button on the left side of the map view allows to draw a new shape. Click in the map to start drawing, click on the first point to finish the drawing.
- (3) Upon closing the shape, a new land use can be assigned to the area. Specify as “Type” the new land use as built-up (new building), tree cover or permanent water bodies. Specify the previous and new relative height, e.g., 0 and 10 if there was no building before and now a 10m tall building is created.

The information is needed to save the polygon, but is only used when new buildings are created instead of vegetation or water and when 3D information is used in the modelling.

(4) Press “Save” to save this polygon.

(5) Polygons can be edited or deleted

(6) Under “Model”, the type of prediction model (recommended: “ANN_2D”) is selected and “Reference” defines the summer day reference as in step 1.

(7) Press “Request” to request the simulation of LST for your custom urban scenario. The run takes 30 seconds to some minutes.

Figure 2-15: The simulation function for creating user-defined scenarios within the EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service (step 2).

Step 3 “Result”: Evaluation of changes in LST upon changes in urban configuration

This step is to explore the changes in land surface temperature resulting from the custom changes in the urban configuration.

Perform following steps (compare with Figure 2-16):

- (1) Select the scenario name under “Simulated changes”
- (2) Set again “Reference days” and “Model” as in steps 1 and 2.
- (3) “Order days” relates to the time when the run was requested (UTC time, i.e. for central European time -2 hours). By this, you can discriminate multiple versions of one scenario (e.g. with small adaptations in the polygons).

The main view shows the **original LST on the left side** and the **LST predicted for the custom scenario on the right side**. You can move a slider in between with this icon .

The modification of the city configuration causes an effect in the distribution of urban heat as indicated by the LST. Adding vegetation or water areas has a cooling effect. In contrary, sealing green spaces by buildings increases the temperature. This effect is most pronounced in the areas which were modified but clearly goes beyond these areas because of neighbourhood effects. Following scientific research, the cooling effect of water is assumed to last at maximum 1 km, while it is 500m for vegetation.

Figure 2-16: Evaluation of changes in urban heat originating from a user-defined scenario within the EO-based Heat Island Simulation and Mitigation Strategies Service (step 3).

2.3.2 UltraHD-based Simulation and Mitigation Services

The UltraHD-based Simulation and Mitigation Services allow to analyse the effect of mitigation activities (e.g., planting trees, or building constructions) with respect to heat, pollution and city airflow related aspects of urban local climate. The manipulation of urban structure can be performed by using a 2D map editor (the so-called Simulation Editor from Section 2.3.3), where another web interface provides information of their induced effects. Hence, the following descriptions of the UltraHD-based Simulation Services summarises the following services:

- Heat Island Simulation Service
- City Airflow Simulation Service
- Pollution Simulation Service

As the purpose of this service is to visualise the impact of local changes on urban characterisation (e.g. by planting trees, new buildings, water bodies) by video and image overlays as well as line charts for time series, the operation of this service requires two steps:

- (1) Creation of manipulated changes and requesting an analysis using the Simulation Editor (see section 2.3.3).
- (2) Investigate results (after completion of the analysis) using the simulation services web page described below.

The completion of a requested analysis requires restarting the UltraHD model loop, which means that the results can be expected after some delay of 1-2 days.

The variants of the services for the themes heat, city airflow and pollution only distinguish from each other by the considered UltraHD parameter. Hence, all the three variants share the same main features:

- Map with zooming functionality.
- Video and image overlays showing the difference between original and manipulated UltraHD model loop.

- Time series data by line-charts for up to three locations showing the difference between original and manipulated UltraHD model loop.
- Overview of analysis requests.

With all these features, the services facilitate the impact estimation of heat island, airflow, and pollution mitigation strategies. Among others, it allows to:

- Inform about the impact of specific theoretical city structure adaptations and to have data-driven reasoning for mitigation measures in real life.
- Optimise city airflow by adapting the city structure to prevent pollution and heat island events.
- Take preventive actions by adapting the city structure.

Figure 2-17: Initial view on the UltraHD Simulation Service.

When entering the UltraHD simulation service (see Figure 2-17), the following options are available:

- (1) Selection of the user and area.
- (2) Selection of the reference day specified when ordering the simulation analysis. The reference day refers to the UltraHD model loop which is used for the analysis.
- (3) In the Simulation Editor to each set of manipulated changes you assign a name. Here you select the set of changes for which you would like to see the analysis outcome.
- (4) Selection of the timestamp, where you have requested the analysis.
- (5) Selection of the parameter for the video overlay.
- (6) Toggle to switch from video overlay and image overlays (see Figure 2-18).

Figure 2-18: Initial view of the UltraHD Simulation Service with activated toggle to select image overlay.

Figure 2-19: UltraHD Simulation Service with overlay selected.

When having an overlay selected, on the webpage the following options are provided (see also Figure 2-19):

- (1) Opens the menu for selecting city area and analysis runs.
- (2) Start the user guide, which explains usage and navigation of the service.
- (3) Opens an overview of past simulation analysis requests, which can also be used to check the status of the analysis order.
- (4) Opens the line charts that show time series data, which is available, if at least one location has been set by using the marker functionality.
- (5) Button to set markers on the map to prepare the time series requests.
- (6) Options for moving and deleting markers.
- (7) Scale showing the difference between the original UltraHD model loop and the model loop with manipulated input data provided by the Simulation Editor.

Figure 2-20: View on the UltraHD Simulation Services with time series results.

If markers have been set on the map, the following options are available for getting time series data (see also Figure 2-20):

- (1) Opens the line chart element on the right-hand-side.
- (2) Selection for choosing the time series parameter.
- (3) Sampling rate of the time series with range 5 and 120 minutes (e.g. sampling rate of 60 minutes means getting a time series with hourly values).
- (4) Export of the time series data in CSV format.
- (5) Trigger the time series request, which is possible having a time series parameter selected.
- (6) Line charts.
- (7) Zooming features of the line chart element.

2.3.3 Simulation Editor

The Simulation Editor is used to manipulate local changes to urban characteristics, and moreover to request an UltraHD model loop using these manipulated changes.

Figure 2-21: Initial view of the Simulation Editor.

When entering the editor, it is required to select a city and corresponding area of interest/bounding box (see Figure 2-21).

Figure 2-22: View on the Simulation Editor after selecting the city area.

If a city area is selected, then so-called simulated changes can be selected or created; see (1) and (2) in Figure 2-22. The selection of “simulated changes” has been assigned a unique name and refers to a set of simulated changes to urban characteristics, that shall be considered when analysing the local impact with respect to the past UltraHD model loop.

Figure 2-23: View on the Simulation Editor when selected an empty set of simulated changes from the selection.

If a set of simulated changes is just created or already existing, the following options are provided (see also Figure 2-23):

- (1) Opens the menu for selection sets of simulated changes and city area.
- (2) Drawing polygons representing different land cover types.
- (3) Options for deletion and moving of drawn polygons.

Figure 2-24: View on the Simulation Editor with open information card for new simulated change. After a completion of a new polygon a pop-up appears (see Figure 2-24) that asks for the following information:

- (1) Landcover type, where currently built-ups, tree cover and water bodies are supported.
- (2) Previous height relative to the terrain height. If not know, enter zero here.
- (3) New height relative to the terrain height.
- (4) Options for save and cancel data input.

Figure 2-25: View on the Simulation Editor when requesting a new analysis run.

When having completed all manipulated changes, then a new analysis run can be requested by specifying in (1) the past UltraHD model loop you like to analysis with respect to the new impact of your local simulations. Clicking on “Request” in (2) registers your request (see Figure 2-25). After that depending on the UltraHD model capacities, your request will be executed with approximate **1 day of waiting time**. If completed, you can see the results on the webpages for the simulation services.

3 Conclusion and Contact

This user guide provides an overview of the features and usage of the commercial CityCLIM City Administration Services as part of the service portfolio of the CityCLIM ecosystem.

Further Information

Furthermore, general information on City Administration Services can be found in the handbook “Towards a Green Future with CityCLIM: A Handbook for Interested Cities” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2023b) or as a short fact sheet in “Deliverable 6.6 - Optimised City Administration Services” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2024). If you are also interested in our Citizen Science approach, have a look at the handbook “Becoming a CityCLIM Citizen Scientist: A Comprehensive Guide” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2023a) to get a broader view of the project.

Get in contact with us

If you have any questions or need advice at any stage, or if you would like to receive updates on CityCLIM or to get further information, please do not hesitate to contact us! To get updates on CityCLIM, you can visit the CityCLIM website at <https://cityclim.eu> and subscribe to the newsletter. You can also follow us on social media platforms such as [Twitter \(X\)](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and, ResearchGate. If you have any questions about the project or are interested in collaboration, you can contact us by filling out the form available on our website. If you would like to contact the CityCLIM administration team regarding the City Administration Services directly, please send an email to the address below.

Contact Us: Email: satelliteservices@ohb-ds.de

Thank you for joining the CityCLIM community.

4 References

CityCLIM Consortium. (2023a). *Becoming a CityCLIM Citizen Scientist: A Comprehensive Guide*.
<https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>

CityCLIM Consortium. (2023b). *Towards a Green Future with CityCLIM: A Handbook for Interested Cities*.
<https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>

CityCLIM Consortium. (2024). *D6.6—Optimised City Administration Services*.
<https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>

About CityCLIM

The strategic objective of CityCLIM is to significantly contribute to delivering the next-generation of City Climate Services based on advanced weather forecast models enhanced with data both from existing, but insufficiently used, sources and emerging data sources, such as satellite data (e.g., Copernicus data) or data generated by Citizens Science approaches for Urban Climate Monitoring etc. For City Climate Services, data products of interest related to land surface properties, atmospheric properties (e.g., aerosol optical thickness), geometry etc. For all of those, information of interest concerns e.g., Copernicus data products and services that are already existing (e.g., based on Sentinel-3/OLCI, PROBA-V, SPOT, Sentinel-1, MetopAS-CAT data), will exist in the near future (based on already flying satellites such as Sentinel-2), or will exist in the mid-term (based on satellites currently under development) and long-term (based on satellites soon starting concept phase) future. The project will establish; (i) an open platform allowing for efficient building of services based on access to diverse data; (ii) enhanced weather models based on data from diverse existing and emerging sources; (iii) a set of City Climate Services customisable to specific needs of users in cities; and (iv) a generic Framework for building next generation of Urban Climate Services. CityCLIM will be driven by 4 Pilots addressing diverse climate regions in Europe (Luxembourg, Thessaloniki, Valencia, Karlsruhe) which will define requirements upon the tools to be developed, support specification and testing of the services and serve as demonstrators of the selected approaches and the developed technologies. The Consortium will elaborate business plan to assure sustainability of the platform and services.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the CityCLIM Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.

© 2024 Copyright in this document remains vested in the CityCLIM Project Partners.

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Development & Integration: A Developer Guide

A comprehensive guide for developers and third party software providers to integrate their own City Climate Services and components into the CityCLIM ecosystem.

September 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036814

Foreword

Dear Reader,

The CityCLIM project introduces an innovative approach to developing technologies that mitigate urban climate change. This developer guide serves as both an introduction and an invitation to developers and third-party software providers interested in extending and enriching our Generic City Climate Platform by integrating additional components and services to build together our ecosystem of next generation City Climate Services.

Our initiative is following the principles of collective expertise and co-development. Therefore, we have outlined the tools and support mechanisms CityCLIM offers to ensure seamless integration for software contributors like you. This developer's guide includes development guidelines with practical examples of integrations and is designed to simplify your first contributions to this dynamic platform.

Sincerely,

The CityCLIM Consortium

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	What CityCLIM offers to third-party software providers	6
3	Developer Manual	7
3.1	CityCLIM Overview: Architecture and GCCP	7
3.2	Development and integration of third-party components and services	9
3.2.1	Integration and Registration.....	10
3.2.2	Storage and Data Management.....	11
3.2.3	Interaction with the CityCLIM ecosystem	13
3.2.4	Monitoring and Alerting.....	15
4	Conclusion, Next Steps and Contact	19
5	References	20

Abbreviations

AM	Access Management	i.e.	id est = that is to say
API	Application Programming Interface	IM	Identity Management
CCS	City Climate Services	JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
D	Deliverable	QoS	Quality of Service
e.g.	Exempli gratia = for example	REST	Representational State Transfer
etc.	et cetera.	RFC	Request for Comments
FP	Full Prototype	SDK	Software Development Kit
GCCP	Generic City Climate Platform	UHD	Ultra High Definition
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol	URL	Uniform Resource Locator

1 Introduction

This document is a guideline and invitation for developers and third-party software providers who are interested in participating in the CityCLIM ecosystem with their own software components and services. It shows the benefits of participation and addresses directly software contributors by providing a comprehensive guide for the development and integration of their own services and software components into the CityCLIM ecosystem.

CityCLIM realised a digital ecosystem which is not limited to components and services developed within the origin project but is open for further developers and third-party software providers who are interested in participating and becoming part of the CityCLIM community. The CityCLIM ecosystem and community offer a platform suitable to exchange knowledge, generate and establish new business models, and cooperate and collaborate for the realisation of further next-generation City Climate Services.

As an enabler, CityCLIM realised the Generic City Climate Platform (GCCP) which is a software platform for City Climate Services (CCS) and backend components that offers standardised, secured and trusted communication within the CityCLIM ecosystem. The genericity of the GCCP enables software providers to participate in the CityCLIM ecosystem with own backend components and own services based on standardised interfaces.

How third-party software providers can benefit from CityCLIM, how they can participate, how they develop and integrate own services and components, and who are contact points if further support is needed, is in detail explained in this document following the structure below:

- **Chapter 2** describes the benefits of a participation in CityCLIM as a software provider. It also introduces which features are offered and gives an impression of what can and need to be done for their own software contributions.
- **Chapter 3** describes technical details of how third-party services and components can be developed, integrated, and registered in the CityCLIM ecosystem and also provides a range of implementation examples as additional material to simplify and support the development process.
- **Chapter 4** shows how to reach our support and contact points for any further information and support.

2 What CityCLIM offers to third-party software providers

The participation as a software provider in CityCLIM comes with a range of benefits and opportunities. First, you become part of a large community with already strong and well know partners (including the CityCLIM core team; see <https://www.cityclim.eu/de/about>) driving the generation and establishment of next-generation City Climate Services. Together we exchange ideas, and cooperate and collaborate on the development, linkage and roll-out of new software components and City Climate Services.

We come with several already implemented real-world City Climate Services successfully deployed in our European wide reference cities serving as initial exploitation areas for our services:

- Luxembourg City in Luxembourg
- Thessaloniki in Greece
- Valencia in Spain
- Karlsruhe in Germany

Becoming a participant in CityCLIM will accelerate your time to this new evolving market with wide exploitation fields. This we achieve by offering the usage of our GCCP to third-party software providers which comes already with a range of usable features and characteristics including:

- A comprehensive RESTful communication API which enables overall communication within components and services in the CityCLIM ecosystem.
- A secured and trusted communication environment realised through encrypted communication, unique software identifiers and API keys.
- An Identity Manager as OpenID Connect Provider offering a Single-Sign-On based authentication and authorisation mechanism usable for customers of your services.
- A data warehouse reachable over a RESTful-API to create, delete, use and monitor scalable storage spaces in our cloud infrastructure enabling to manage your data just for storing or to share with other components or services.
- A monitoring system which provides comprehensive Quality of Service (QoS) information, live data and alerts for your services and components.
- Several software components and services already in use, which data could be used as a basis/input for your developments.

Using all features of the GCCP enables third-party software providers to focus on their core business activities and reduces the work to few tasks, e.g.:

- Development and optimisation of software components and services.
- Easy integration and registration of the software components and services into the CityCLIM ecosystem.
- Attracting your target group to use your components and services.

3 Developer Manual

This chapter provides a technical overview of the CityCLIM software architecture, provided interfaces, processes and methods and describes how third-party software providers can develop, integrate and register further software components or services, how they can use the features of the GCCP and how they can use/link with components and services already operating in the CityCLIM ecosystem.

3.1 CityCLIM Overview: Architecture and GCCP

To introduce the CityCLIM ecosystem, this section describes the overall CityCLIM architecture and the software architecture of the GCCP.

Figure 3-1: Overall CityCLIM architecture.

Figure 3-1 shows the conceptual CityCLIM architecture which is a composition of four major modules:

- **Generic City Climate Platform** – The GCCP is the platform that connects operational software components such as Data Processors, which prepare raw data from connected data sources for further use within the CityCLIM ecosystem, and Engines, which create value out of prepared data that can be used by connected CCS, the end user services. The GCCP also acts as a data warehouse and provides a range of features to ensure a secure and trusted communication environment.
- **Data Sources** – Multiple data sources are connected to the CityCLIM ecosystem ranging from in-situ data to earth observation data.

- **Proprietary Weather Platform** – Showcases the connection of self-hosted third-party component and provides weather forecast information to engines hosted in the GCCP.
- **City Climate Services** – Are representing the next-generation City Climate Services and show a range of already implemented CCS.
- **Pilot users** – Represent the end users of CCS in our 4 reference cities. CCS may be customised for specific end-users in terms of language, usage behaviour, designs or further specific requirements.

A more detailed description of the overall CityCLIM architecture is given in “D1.3 – Public CityCLIM Concept” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2022).

Figure 3-2: GCCP Software Architecture.

After giving an overview on the overall CityCLIM architecture, Figure 3-2 focuses on the software architecture of the GCCP where third-party components and services need to be integrated and registered. The yellow boxes are highlighting the components which are building the GCCP. The red boxes are highlighting the components and services connected to the platform and operating within the CityCLIM ecosystem. The purple boxes show how your self-hosted services and components would be integrated into the CityCLIM ecosystem. Furthermore, outside of the software architecture are located different users, as well as connected external data sources.

Table 3-1 gives a brief introduction into the yellow boxes/components that are building the GCCP.

Table 3-1: Introduction of components building the GCCP.

GCCP Component		Brief description
Metric Monitoring (MM)		Provides GCCP metric collection capacities, and support for visualization of these metrics (e.g., performance, service usage, data access, ...).
Access Management (AM)		The GCCP component for managing external requests, which includes management aspects as routing, rate limiting, load balancing for APIs and DDoS protection for website endpoints.
Identity Management (IM)		The identity management system to integrate authentication and authorization mechanisms (e.g., Single-Sign On, account and token management)

GCCP Component	Brief description
Middleware	The management of external services by generic standardised APIs, access to data warehouses, and tracking of relevant information for metric monitoring. Usage of cloud-provider specific Software Developments Kits (SDK).
Data Warehouse	Data spaces for structured and unstructured data types.

As a third-party software provider who wants to operate their own self-hosted components and services within the CityCLIM ecosystem, you will in get in contact with these components in the development and integration process.

3.2 Development and integration of third-party components and services

Following an overview of the CityCLIM architecture and GCCP, this section outlines the steps that third-party service and component providers need to take to develop, integrate, and operate their components and services within the CityCLIM ecosystem.

Figure 3-3 shows the GCCP use cases relevant for third-party service and component provider which are described in Table 3-2.

Figure 3-3: Use Cases for third-party Service and Component Providers.

Table 3-2: Descriptions of Use Cases for third-party Service and Component Providers.

Use cases	Description
Integration & Registration	Integration and registration of self-hosted third-party components or services into the GCCP ecosystem.
Storage and Data Management	Storage and Data management using the GCCP, which includes the creation/reservation of new storage spaces, data upload and data download, data space monitoring and further storage organisational aspects.
Interaction with the CityCLIM ecosystem	Interaction/communication with other components and services operating in the CityCLIM ecosystem.
Monitoring and Alerting	Monitoring and visualisation of metrics (e.g., performance, service usage, data access, etc.) and alerting for third-party components and services.

The following sections explain in detail the implementation of these use cases.

3.2.1 Integration and Registration

The GCCP allows participation to the CityCLIM ecosystem by the interaction with a personal user account or when implementing new services by a machine-to-machine communication. Both ways rely on state-of-the-art security policies and protocols.

All necessary links, access data and relevant data for configuration will be provided after you got in contact with us (see section 4).

3.2.1.1 Interaction by a personal user account

A dedicated webpage allows users to register to the CityCLIM ecosystem.

On the bottom of the sign-in page (see Figure 3-4) click on “Register” to get to the registration page (see Figure 3-6).

Complete the registration form and click on “Register”. After a few moments, an email with a confirmation link will be sent. Clicking on this link completes the registration process.

Figure 3-4: Sign-In page.

Figure 3-6: Registration page.

To change account information, such as name or email address, or to delete the account, navigate to the sign-in page, sign in, and on the account page, click “Personal info”. In the upcoming page (see Figure 3-5), perform the needed actions.

After successful registration, contact the technical team of CityCLIM again so that an authorized use of the requested interfaces specified in OpenAPI is ensured.

Figure 3-5: Account Management Page.

To interact with RESTful CityCLIM interfaces, include your user credentials in the headers of each request by assigning your username and password to the header keys “USERNAME” and “PASSWORD”. Additionally, a middleware and security software developer kit (in Python) (introduced in section 3.2.2) can be provided to facilitate the communication with the platform.

The personal user account login is designed to be used especially for manual, low-frequent interaction with the CityCLIM ecosystem, which could be interesting, e.g., for data acquisition or testing.

3.2.1.2 Interaction via machine-to-machine communication

When extending the CityCLIM ecosystem by new services or components, authentication processes may occur at high frequency and require a time-efficient implementation. In that case, the GCCP supports a machine-to-machine communication approach, which involves the assignment of a unique API key. This way enables communication between the new service or component and the existing portfolio of CityCLIM and is in fact applied to all processing components of CityCLIM.

This registration process requires contact with the administration team of CityCLIM to ensure effective integration to the platform. The following steps are required:

- **Step 1:** Contact the technical support team of CityCLIM using the contact provided in section 4 for registration of the new service or component.
- **Step 2:** The technical support provides a token we refer as the “API key” which can be used for authentication and authorisation.
- **Step 3:** Attach the API key to the header key “api_key” of each request.

If, moreover, the service shall be integrated to the metric monitoring system of the GCCP, then the following information is required:

- URL of the service or component
- specification of interfaces
- service name.

Additionally, registration of a CityCLIM user account is needed (see Section 3.2.1.1), which is used for entering the monitoring dashboards.

3.2.2 Storage and Data Management

The GCCP provides an API framework that handles data management and operations of integrated components and 3rd party services with respect to the Data Warehouse by APIs. These APIs are established by using cloud provider specific SDKs, and so are generic in the sense, that they offer data management and data operations that have no specific use cases, but rather cover the following general functionalities:

- Management of storage space (e.g., creation, deletion, internal storage-type specific organisation)
- Upload, patching, download, and deletion of (multiple) data (with bulk operations support)
- Querying data with filtering options to receive requested entities or corresponding metadata.

The functionality of the middleware is not one-to-one with the integrated cloud provider specific SDKs. In fact, it extends the portfolio by adding additional functionalities (e.g., bulk operations), which are not offered by the selected cloud providers. Each storage type has dedicated APIs for data operation actions and management.

blobs	tables	storage management
GET /blob/read/list_names Read Unstructured Data List	POST /table/write/entities Write Multiple Structured Data	GET /storage Info Storage
GET /blob/read/walk Read Unstructured Data Walk	DELETE /table/remove/query Remove Structured Data Query	DELETE /storage Delete Storage
POST /blob/read/entities Read Unstructured Data Entities	POST /table/write/entity Write Structured Data	POST /storage Create Storage
DELETE /blob/remove/entity Remove Unstructured Data Entity	POST /table/remove/entities Remove Multiple Structured Data	GET /storage/table Info Table Storage
GET /blob/read/entity Read Unstructured Data Entity	POST /table/read/entities Read Multiple Structured Data	POST /storage/table Create Table Storage
POST /blob/write/entity Write Unstructured Data Entity	POST /table/remove/entity Remove Structured Data	DELETE /storage/table Delete Table Storage
POST /blob/write/entities Write Multiple Unstructured Data Entities	POST /table/read/entity Read Structured Data Entity	POST /storage/blob Create Blob Container
POST /blob/read/entities/pool Bulk Download Pool	POST /table/read/query Read Structured Data Query	DELETE /storage/blob Delete Blob Container
GET /blob/read/exists Read Unstructured Data Exists	PATCH /table/update/entity Update Structured Data	GET /storage/blob Info Blob Container
POST /blob/read/entities/threading Bulk Download Threading Chunks	PATCH /table/update/entities Patch Multiple Structured Data	

Figure 3-7: Overview of generic APIs available in the middleware FP.

A technical documentation for all APIs is available in accordance with the OpenAPI specification¹ and will be provided when you contact us. To support the usage of the GCCP APIs a SDK (in Python) has been developed, which additionally accelerates the development of new services based on the CityCLIM platform. The so-called middleware SDK offers a programmatic approach to its API layer and includes all security relevant aspects. Figure 3-8 gives an impression of the SDK.

```

from cityclimmiddleware import MiddlewareClient

if __name__ == "__main__":
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT = MiddlewareClient()

    # TABLE
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.read.query()
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.write.entity()
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.write.entities()
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.remove.entities()

    # BLOB
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.blob.read.entities()
    MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.blob.write.entity()

    (method) def query(
        storage_id: str,
        query_filter: str | None = None,
        select: list[str] | None = None,
        parameters: dict = {},
        security_config: SecurityConfig | None = None
    ) -> (bytes | Any | Response)

```

Figure 3-8: Initialisation of the Middleware Client using the Middleware SDK, including of an indication of different methods simplifying the access to the GCCP Data Warehouse.

To provide an implementation example for the storage and data management, the workflow of the Simulation Engine of the CityCLIM ecosystem is used. The Simulation Engine of the CityCLIM ecosystem is responsible for managing the workflows required to enable the so-called Simulation and Mitigation Services (see CityCLIM Consortium, 2024a). A prominent workflow of the simulation engine is the manipulation of earth observation data based on user-provided inputs. These inputs are given by polygons in JSON format, which define manipulated changes to local urban structures.

In this example, to accelerate and simplify transactions with the CityCLIM Data Warehouse, the middleware SDK is used in the implementation of the simulation engine, which now highlights several steps of the mentioned workflow.

By a dedicated web interface called the Simulation Editor (see CityCLIM Consortium, 2024a), the user can make the manipulated changes to local urban structure. The Middleware SDK supports the maintenance of user-provided changes, providing methods for writing (see Figure 3-9), updating (see Figure 3-10), and removing (see Figure 3-11) structured entities.

¹ See <https://github.com/OAI/OpenAPI-Specification/>

```
response: requests.Response = MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.write.entity(
    storage_id=SETTINGS.STORAGE_ID_UHD_POLYGONS, entity=entity
)
```

Figure 3-9: Middleware SDK example for writing structured entities.

```
response: requests.Response = MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.update.entities(
    storage_id=SETTINGS.STORAGE_ID_UHD_POLYGONS, entities=entities
)
```

Figure 3-10: Middleware SDK example for updating structured entities.

```
response: requests.Response = MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.remove.entities(
    storage_id=SETTINGS.STORAGE_ID_UHD_POLYGONS, identifiers=identifiers
)
```

Figure 3-11: Middleware SDK example for removing structured entities.

As a preparation of the earth observation data manipulation, user-provided polygons from the Data Warehouse are requested using a method that allows to query structured data based on a query (see Figure 3-12).

```
content = MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.table.read.query(
    storage_id=SETTINGS.STORAGE_ID_UHD_POLYGONS, query_filter=query_filter
)
```

Figure 3-12: Middleware SDK example for requesting user-provided polygons from the Data Warehouse.

When the manipulation of the earth observation data is completed, the result is uploaded by the following method (see Figure 3-13).

```
MIDDLEWARE_CLIENT.blob.write.entity(
    storage_id=storage_id,
    blob_name=blob_name,
    file_name=file_name,
    content=content,
    overwrite=True,
)
```

Figure 3-13: Middleware SDK example for uploading results.

3.2.3 Interaction with the CityCLIM ecosystem

The CityCLIM ecosystem utilises various data types and offers service applications in the scope of the climate change induced challenges of urban areas by the integration of different processing workflows.

Figure 3-14: Components of the CityCLIM ecosystem with GCCP modules (yellow), and CCS specific modules (red).

Besides graphical web interfaces to the developed services, the CityCLIM ecosystems provides technical access to various datasets and processing workflows, orchestrating all services, components and the GCCP itself (see Figure 3-14).

A selection of such dataset access and processing workflows is listed below:

- On-demand model time series data via API for specific locations for supported regions.
- API for receiving warnings with respect to heat exposure.
- A dedicated interface for searching and downloading earth observation data.
- Beyond-state-of-the-art model-based weather forecast data and post-processed results in image and video formats.
- On-demand statistical analysis over a larger period (e.g., summer months) using aggregated weather model data to identify urban areas heavily affected by the urban heat effect.
- Data injection to proprietary infrastructure (e.g., smart city platforms) after completion of workflows (e.g., daily weather forecast completion)

The technical documentation is following the OpenAPI specification, and up-to-date documentation for relevant interfaces can be provided when requested.

To demonstrate an interaction with a component operating within the CityCLIM ecosystem, the following endpoint in Table 3-3 is specified, which provides time series data of the UHD model run for different locations.

Table 3-3: Specification of an example endpoint for time series data provision.

Get UltraHD model run time series	
POST	/operational/time-series-pointwise
Query Parameters	
user_id	ID of the user
bbox_name	Name of the supported region
parameter_name	Name of the UltraHD model parameter
model_run_start_timestamp	Starting date of the UHD model run in the format. YEAR-MONTH-DAYT00:00:00. E.g., 2023-06-08T00:00:00
period	Integer number between 5 and 120 (boundary included). This number describes the sampling rate of the time series.
HEADER	
USERNAME	Your username
PASSWORD	Your password
BODY	
<pre>[{ "pointId": "Central area", "coords": { "lat": 49.017552773601196, "lng": 8.399215384591711 } }]</pre>	

3.2.4 Monitoring and Alerting

The GCCP provides a monitoring and alerting tool for components and services operating in the CityCLIM ecosystem. Each third-party component and service provider can get access to a pre-configured web-based dashboard visualising valuable information about the

- performance (e.g., statistics about component/service calls, latencies, or amount of data exchanged),
- analyse metrics (e.g., debug information and meta-data about messages, anomalies, or error codes, but also interesting metrics for market analyses showing anonymised data on the postal code level from where especially services are accessed, including statistics about top countries and cities) and
- QoS information (like average, min, or max values per hour for several metrics like latencies, data amount transferred, or count of called components and services) of their operating services and components.

A monitoring dashboard can be requested from the GCCP administration team once a component or service has been registered and integrated into Identity Management and is operational within the CityCLIM ecosystem. This allows third-party component and service providers to access the web-based dashboard and view all of the above metrics for their services and components.

In addition, custom monitoring dashboards can be requested to visualise additional metrics or calculations/transformations of them. The following metrics are monitored by default by the GCCP and can be used for this purpose (see Figure 3-15 for an overview and Table 3-4 for the description of the different parameters).

```

6   "_source": {
7     "@timestamp": "2024-03-13T11:46:13Z",
8     "status": 200,
9     "path": "/middleware/",
10    "method": "GET",
11    "route_name": "Middleware",
12    "month_year": "03_2024",
13    "latency_in_ms": 210,
14    "request_size_in_bytes": 769,
15    "geo_location": {
16      "country_code": "DE",
17      "country_name": "Germany",
18      "region_or_state": "Nordrhein-Westfalen",
19      "city": "Dusseldorf"
20    }
21  },

```

Figure 3-15: Example for metrics that are monitored by the GCCP.

Table 3-4: Description of monitored metrics.

Parameter	Description
@timestamp	The time the request was received.
status	HTTP status code to indicate whether a request was successful or not.
path	The requested URL path, which can provide detailed analysis of the specific functionality used by a service.
method	HTTP method of the request.
route_name	Name of the GCCP component or service addressed.
latency_in_ms	Time between the incoming request and the returned response.
request_size_in_bytes	The size of an incoming network packet.
geo_location	A set of metrics concerning the location from which the request was sent anonymised on postal code level.
country_code	A code acting as abbreviation for a country name.
country_name	The concrete country name.
region_or_state	Region or state in a country.
city	City on a specific region.

Finally, the tool provides an alerting feature that can be used to customise alerts based on thresholds or other conditions. This allows third-party components and service providers to configure custom alerts through the web-based interface. The configuration process involves defining several key elements, including the alert rule name, a suitable query to retrieve the necessary data for the alert, the alert condition, the alert evaluation behaviour, and details for your alert rule (such as a summary to facilitate more effective alert management). The alerting tool is based on Grafana, a comprehensive documentation on configuring alerts can be found under <https://grafana.com/docs/grafana/latest/alerting>.

The following figures show exemplarily the monitoring on a component with the name “Forecast-Engine” with metrics over a 30-day period (generally configurable from live data over specific time periods or over the last few days/weeks/months/years).

Figure 3-16 shows the calls of the component/engine over the selected time period. It shows the total calls (first panel) and the calls as a time series (second panel).

Figure 3-16: Component calls for a selected time period.

Figure 3-17 shows a panel for accessing metadata for every message the component exchanged. It also provides further filtering options to navigate through large amounts of meta-information/messages. A click on a cell in the “_source” column shows the complete meta-data in a new window helpful to analyse single messages in more detail.

Figure 3-17: Meta information of exchanged messages.

Figure 3-18 shows some performance metrics. In this example is show the latencies in milliseconds in the first panel and the sizes of exchanged messages in the second panel as a time series view.

Figure 3-18: Performance metrics about latencies and sizes of exchanged messages.

Figure 3-19 shows panels for the HTTP response status codes² that support monitoring of a successful communication. The first panel shows in a time series view the codes and the second panel shows only anomalies which are classified as “not status 200” indicating an unsuccessful communication helpful as additional information to identify errors and anomalies.

Figure 3-19: Metrics about HTTP codes and anomalies.

Figure 3-20 and Figure 3-21 show panels on the usage of a component or service. Figure 3-20 shows the panel for visualising the geolocation of accesses on an anonymised postcode level, and Figure 3-21 shows panels for statistics such as the top countries and cities accessing the component or service. Insights into the usage can help third-party components and service providers to make better business decisions.

² Various status codes are existing. The monitoring and alerting tool monitors successful responses (200–299), indicating the request was successfully received, understood, and accepted; redirection messages (300–399), informing the client that further action is needed to complete the request; client error responses (400–499), indicating that there was an error with the request from the client's side; and server error responses (500–599), indicating that the server failed to fulfil a valid request due to an error on the server side. See for more details in RFC 9110: <https://httpwg.org/specs/rfc9110.html#overview.of.status.codes>

Figure 3-20: Geo-location showing from where services and components are called.

Figure 3-21: Statistics about top countries and cities.

Finally, Figure 3-22 shows some QoS metrics about average, minimum, and maximum usage per hour in the exemplary 30 days' time period.

Figure 3-22: QoS statistics for different metrics.

The figures above give an impression of the monitoring and alerting tool. In addition to these default visualisation panels for each component and service, third-party services and component providers can request further customised dashboards and configure alerts to trigger notification via email, Slack, or other communication channel based on individually configured conditions.

4 Conclusion, Next Steps and Contact

Join CityCLIM as a Software Partner

Urban centres globally are facing intricate challenges related to Urban Heat Islands, distinct microclimatic variations, and the pressing imperative of sustainable urban development. CityCLIM offers state-of-the-art, scientifically-advanced next generation city climate services meticulously designed to address the unique climatic complexities of today's urban landscapes. To third-party software providers, CityCLIM offers an exciting opportunity to contribute to this rapidly growing ecosystem and emerging market by collaborating with leading experts and helping shape the future of urban climate resilience.

Designed to enable a seamless, fast, and secure integration of your services and components, the Generic City Climate Platform (GCCP) provides the needed tools to do this with minimal effort using secured and standardised interfaces, robust data management, and strong community support. CityCLIM provides a collaborative environment where you can build and showcase your services while leveraging the strengths of an established network and platform.

How to Get Started

This manual already provided an overview of what CityCLIM offers to you as a third-party software provider and how you are able to develop and integrate third-party components and services. To join CityCLIM as a Software Partner and begin your journey, follow these steps:

- **Understand your benefits and opportunities** – CityCLIM offers a chance to enter a new emerging market for next generation City Climate Services. Explore this opportunity and the benefits offered by CityCLIM, including an already strong and growing community, a feature-rich platform that enables rapid time-to-market, and think about your own promising business models.
- **Get familiar with the GCCP and get in contact with us** – Familiarise yourself with the capabilities and features of the GCCP and how the GCCP supports you in focussing on your goals. If you have any questions, get in contact with us (see below)!
- **Develop & integrate your services in the CityCLIM ecosystem** - Start developing your components and services and start with the integration process using the detailed guidelines in this document.
- **Collaborate with the CityCLIM community** - Exchange ideas with other partners, explore synergies with other existing components and services, and build new solutions that extend and innovate the CityCLIM ecosystem.

Further Information

Refer to further public material as “D2.4 - Optimised Full Prototype of Generic City Climate Platform” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2024b) to get a short fact sheet on the GCCP or the handbooks “Towards a Green Future with CityCLIM: A Handbook for Interested Cities” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2023b) and “Becoming a CityCLIM Citizen Scientist: A Comprehensive Guide” (CityCLIM Consortium, 2023a) to get a broader view of the project.

Get in contact with us

If you have any questions or need advice at any stage, or if you would like to receive updates on CityCLIM, please do not hesitate to contact us! To get updates and further information on CityCLIM, you can visit the CityCLIM website at <https://cityclim.eu> and subscribe to the newsletter. You can also follow us on social media platforms such as [Twitter \(X\)](#), and [LinkedIn](#), and ResearchGate. If you have any questions about the project or are interested in collaboration, you can contact us by filling out the form available on our website. If you are interested in integrating and registering your own services and components, please send an email to the CityCLIM administration team (see email below).

Contact Us: Email: satelliteservices@ohb-ds.de

Thank you for joining the CityCLIM community.

5 References

- CityCLIM Consortium. (2022). *D1.3 -Public CityCLIM Concept*. <https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>
- CityCLIM Consortium. (2023a). *Becoming a CityCLIM Citizen Scientist: A Comprehensive Guide*. <https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>
- CityCLIM Consortium. (2023b). *Towards a Green Future with CityCLIM: A Handbook for Interested Cities*. <https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>
- CityCLIM Consortium. (2024a). *City Administration Services: A User Guide*. <https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>
- CityCLIM Consortium. (2024b). *D2.4—Optimised Full Prototype of Generic City Climate Platform*. <https://www.cityclim.eu/info-material>

About CityCLIM

The strategic objective of CityCLIM is to significantly contribute to delivering the next-generation of City Climate Services based on advanced weather forecast models enhanced with data both from existing, but insufficiently used, sources and emerging data sources, such as satellite data (e.g., Copernicus data) or data generated by Citizens Science approaches for Urban Climate Monitoring etc. For City Climate Services, data products of interest related to land surface properties, atmospheric properties (e.g., aerosol optical thickness), geometry etc. For all of those, information of interest concerns e.g., Copernicus data products and services that are already existing (e.g., based on Sentinel-3/OLCI, PROBA-V, SPOT, Sentinel-1, MetopAS-CAT data), will exist in the near future (based on already flying satellites such as Sentinel-2), or will exist in the mid-term (based on satellites currently under development) and long-term (based on satellites soon starting concept phase) future. The project will establish; (i) an open platform allowing for efficient building of services based on access to diverse data; (ii) enhanced weather models based on data from diverse existing and emerging sources; (iii) a set of City Climate Services customizable to specific needs of users in cities; and (iv) a generic Framework for building next generation of Urban Climate Services. CityCLIM will be driven by 4 Pilots addressing diverse climate regions in Europe (Luxembourg, Thessaloniki, Valencia, Karlsruhe) which will define requirements upon the tools to be developed, support specification and testing of the services and serve as demonstrators of the selected approaches and the developed technologies. The consortium will elaborate business plan to assure sustainability of the platform and services.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the CityCLIM Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.

© 2024 Copyright in this document remains vested in the CityCLIM Project Partners.

Funded by the Horizon 2020
Framework Programme of the
European Union

